

MARINEWIND

Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)

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D6.5: Data Management Plan

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

TABLE OF CONTENTS	3
TABLE OF TABLES.....	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	5
1 PROJECT OVERVIEW.....	6
2 RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT IN MARINEWIND	7
2.1 OBJECTIVES OF THE DMP.....	7
2.2 THE OVERALL STRUCTURE OF THE DATA MANAGEMENT IN MARINEWIND	7
2.3 DATA MANAGEMENT DURING MARINEWIND LIFETIME	8
2.4 LONG TERM DATA MANAGEMENT.....	8
3 DATA COLLECTION AND INTEROPERABILITY.....	8
3.1 DATA INFORMATION	8
3.2 ORGANISATION OF DATA COLLECTED	9
3.3 DATA COLLECTED FOR EACH MARINEWIND WORK PACKAGE.....	10
3.3.1 WORK PACKAGE 1	10
3.3.2 WORK PACKAGE 2	10
3.3.3 WORK PACKAGE 3	11
3.3.4 WORK PACKAGE 4	12
3.3.5 WORK PACKAGE 5	12
3.3.6 WORK PACKAGE 6	13
4 DATA STORAGE AND BACK-UP	13
5 DATA DOCUMENTATION.....	14
6 DATA ACCESS.....	16
7 DATA SHARING AND REUSE.....	17
8 DATA PRESERVATION AND ARCHIVING.....	17
9 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	17

10 PRIVACY OF PARTICIPANTS17

TABLE OF TABLES

Table 1 - Metadata included in the readme file of MARINEWIND data..... 15
Table 2 - Examples of files identification..... 15

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The current document, titled MARINEWIND DMP, has been developed within the framework of the MARINEWIND project, which is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N° 101075572.

This deliverable describes the data management process for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by the MARINEWIND project. As part of making research data findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable (FAIR), the Data Management Plan (DMP) provides a summary of the main elements to consider in the definition of the MARINEWIND data management policy to be used by project partners throughout the project activities. The DMP will provide indications about the management of all the data generated during the project activities, including how data will be collected, managed, stored, and made available during the project and how they will be shared upon MARINEWIND completion.

1 PROJECT OVERVIEW

MARINEWIND is a 36-month Coordination and Support Action that will identify bottlenecks and potential opportunities to strengthen **Floating Offshore Wind Technology (FOWT)** role in delivering innovative solutions to system integration and will consider how best to integrate such a system by exploring the market, policy and regulations issues, social, financial, and techno-economic optimal solutions, and provision for storage and flexibility recommendations.

The MARINEWIND methodology is based on the analysis of the MARINEWIND Labs, which are social, environmental, technological, and financial pilot studies based upon a multi-faceted data collection and analysis on barriers and enablers related to:

- a) policy measures (**WP1**),
- b) societal engagement and environmental impact (**WP2**),
- c) financial solutions, techno-economic implications, and commercialisation of FOWTs (**WP3**).

The **MARINEWIND Labs** are in five countries: **Portugal and UK (actual applications of FOWTs) and Greece, Spain, and Italy (planned applications of FOWTs)**. These Labs will support the transfer of knowledge from the established experiences to the potential FOWT sites where plans for installation of FOWTs are still at various stages of planning or implementation.

The MARINEWIND Labs will involve the **Quintuple Helix stakeholders (industry, academia, public authorities, civil society, and green innovation)**. The threefold analysis will be conveyed into the **MARINEWIND web based Geographical Information System (webGIS)** which will provide specifically tailored information on FOWT to the various stakeholders based on their category, geographical location and their goals and policy recommendations on how to have more informed RES policies and how to increase societal acceptance (**WP4**).

The Replicability Plan will support the transfer of knowledge. **Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation activities (WP5)** will ensure widespread outreach of the project results and outcomes and to reach its impacts.

2 RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT IN MARINEWIND

2.1 Objectives of the DMP

Accessibility of the data during the project lifetime and beyond, and long-term data preservation are the ultimate goals of an effective data management, which is therefore an essential aspect of each research project, and it must be thoroughly planned since the early stages of the project. This deliverable aims at describing the overall data management process within MARINEWIND: how data will be collected, managed, stored, and made available during the project lifetime, and how they will be stored and shared upon MARINEWIND completion. It is worth to point out that a proper data management plan can mitigate the risk of data loss or other threats that could render the data illegible or unusable.

Good data management is not a goal, but it is essential for knowledge discovery and innovation, as it stimulates data and knowledge integration and reuse by the community after the data publication process¹. Given this, all data collected and generated during the MARINEWIND project will be managed following the FAIR principles to be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

The management of the data produced during the project will aim to ensure open access taking also into consideration the “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” principle, to ensure the adoption of suitable measures to preserve project results that can be further commercially exploited in the future (e.g., through patenting). Thus, the project will seek a balance between openness and protection of information, commercialization, and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), privacy concerns, security etc. In case project partners need to keep specific parts of their research data closed, the choice will be explicitly justified in the DMP.

2.2 The overall structure of the Data Management in MARINEWIND

This deliverable firstly describes the Data Collection within MARINEWIND, presented in Section 3. This section describes the methods of data collection for each Work Package (WP), as indicated by the Work Package Leaders. For each WP, the following items are checked and described, as far as applicable: type of data, aim of the data, formats, origin of the data and estimated size. The Data Collection section is essential to give a brief description of the data, including any existing data or third-party sources that will be used, providing information about its content, type, and coverage.

The Section 4 will then describe where and how the data generated by the project activities will be stored. Information about the IT infrastructure used will be also provided.

The Section 5 will detail how data will be documented to ensure that new members of the MARINEWIND team and/or any possible (secondary) users are able to understand and reuse the data. Additional information will be provided about the metadata used to provide indications about the identification and access to the data.

¹ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

The Section 6 will mainly describe the level of data confidentiality and the responsibility of the individual organisations, within MARINEWIND, involved in the data collection process while the Section 7 will describe how the data will be shared and where they will be deposited.

Preserving all the material produced by the project will be a challenge. The Section 8 will therefore explain the general rules adopted by the project to preserve the main part of data generated. A brief explanation of the allocation of resources will be provided in Section 9.

Finally, Section 10 will detail the procedures to ensure the privacy of Participants to MARINEWIND activities.

2.3 Data management during MARINEWIND lifetime

The DMP will be updated at the end of the first reporting period (M18, April 2024). APRE will be responsible for coordinating the data management with the active support of WP Leaders and Task Leaders. The content of the data management plan will be reanalysed and enriched in the update of the deliverable according to the project implementation progresses.

2.4 Long term data management

To be useful, findable and reusable over the long-term, data will be stored on ZENODO, that will automatically assign a persistent identifier, namely a DOI, to datasets to allow easy citation and discoverability. By archiving on ZENODO, the long-term preservation will be guaranteed, avoiding the risk of data loss.

3 DATA COLLECTION AND INTEROPERABILITY

3.1 Data information

During the MARINEWIND project, various types of data will be collected. This section describes the methods of data collection for each WP as indicated by the WP Leaders. For each WP, the following items are checked and described, as far as applicable.

Type of Data

In research projects, usually different types of data may be collected and documented. Since MARINEWIND is a Coordination and Support Action, no research data will be collected. However, the following categories of data will be collected in the project:

- **Technical Data:** recorded information related to technical/scientific activities (e.g., analysis of existing practices, development of new solutions, etc.). The collection may require surveys, interviews, instruments to record, transformation of existing datasets to create new data, etc.
- **Stakeholders' Data:** such as Contact Details or any other (personal) data of MARINEWIND stakeholders. The collection may involve registration forms to event, newsletter subscription,

website login, and so on. The handling of those data will consider GDPR.

It is worth to point out that administrative/financial data is not included in the technical data definition, and in MARINEWIND project it will be considered other data. Moreover, the identified categories can occasionally overlap, and data can belong to more than one category depending on the specificities of the data itself.

Aim of the data

For each WP a short description of the aim of the data produced linked to the objectives of the Work Package is provided.

Format of the data and interoperability

Research data come in various formats: text, numeric, multimedia, models, software languages, discipline, and instrument specific, and so on. For each WP, it will be described the format of the data produced, with the goal to facilitate the accessibility and interoperability of the data, giving preferences to open and standard formats. Being MARINEWIND a Coordination and Support Action, none of the data collected will require specific formats or methodologies for collection that could represent an obstacle to interoperability.

3.2 Organisation of collected data

The data collected within MARINEWIND will be organised taking into consideration the following aspects, as far as applicable.

Version Control

To overcome the challenge of managing and tracking research material, especially in collaborative projects, data will be organized to keep track of different versions of the datasets, through the application of a version control system. A version control system (or revision control system) is a system that tracks incremental versions (or revisions) of files and, in some cases, directories over time. Improving the ability to consistently track and retrieve each version of a file can lead to more efficient collaboration and increased accuracy of research results. Through the version control system, the risk of losing information after modifications is minimised.

Versioning is important for long term-research data management where metadata and/or files are updated over time.

Naming conventions

With the overall aim to make the data accessible (and ultimately foster reproducible research), MARINEWIND datasets will be carefully named by choosing file names that are informative and useful for both humans and machines. Name should be meaningful so to make easier for others to understand what the file contains and how it should be used. Below we present are some examples of naming conventions within MARINEWIND:

Choosing machine readable names

Use deliberate delimits. Common approach is using “_” and “-” to delimit units of metadata in the file names. A general rule could be to use “-” to separate words you want to glob together and “_” to separate different information within a file name. Don’t use spaces, punctuation, capital letters or special characters (Using \$, @, %, #, &*, (,), !, etc. may have meanings in programming languages).

Choosing human readable names

Choose names that explain the content. The more meaningful the name, the more useful it is for human users. The more metadata you store in the name, the less you need to explain elsewhere. Choose short names.

3.3 Data collected for each MARINEWIND Work Package

3.3.1 Work Package 1

Type of collected data

- Technical data
- Stakeholders data
- Other

Aim of data collected in WP1

WP1 – ‘Policy framework assessment and co-creation’ will produce a state-of-the-art assessment of policy and whole market design barriers and enablers to provide a broad knowledge base of opportunities for innovation in the offshore floating wind sector. A dedicated task will engage the MARINEWIND Quintuple Helix stakeholders to assess and validate critical barriers and enabling features impacting legal, institutional, political frameworks, social and environmental issues for development and industrial rollout stage of offshore wind (feeding all WPs).

Format of collected data

- ✓ DOC /.DOCX
- ✓ .XLS / .XLSX
- ✓ .PPT / .PPTX
- ✓ .CSV
- ✓ .PDF
- ✓ Photo Format (e.g., .JPEG, .PNG)
- ✓ Video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .AVI)

3.3.2 Work Package 2

Type of collected data

- Technical data

Stakeholders data

Other

Aim of data collected in WP2

WP2 – ‘Social acceptance and environmental impact analyses will deal with a state-of-the-art analysis of barriers and enablers for societal engagement and environmental impact to provide a broad knowledge base of the policy and market situations of renewable energy, in the FOWT.

Format of collected data

- ✓ DOC /.DOCX
- ✓ .XLS / .XLSX
- ✓ .PPT / .PPTX
- ✓ .CSV
- ✓ .PDF
- ✓ Photo Format (e.g., .JPEG, .PNG)
- ✓ Video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .AVI)

3.3.3 Work Package 3

Type of collected data

Technical data

Stakeholders data

Other

Aim of data collected in WP3

WP3 – ‘Financing, techno-economic analysis and survey’ will provide a broad knowledge base of financial and market analysis and financial solutions at Labs and European level concerning FOWT. The WP will also cover activities related to the analysis of technological barriers and enablers to support the deployment of the FOWT.

Format of collected data

- ✓ DOC /.DOCX
- ✓ .XLS / .XLSX
- ✓ .PPT / .PPTX
- ✓ .CSV
- ✓ .PDF
- ✓ Photo Format (e.g., .JPEG, .PNG)
- ✓ Video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .AVI)

3.3.4 Work Package 4

Type of collected data

- Technical data
- Stakeholders data
- Other

Aim of data collected in WP4

WP4 – ‘Development of MARINEWIND Tools’ will be centred around the creation of a web multifunctional tool providing specifically tailored information to the various stakeholders on the basis of their category, geographical location and on their goals. Additionally, recommendations, webinars and a replicability plan will be developed.

Format of collected data

- ✓ DOC /.DOCX
- ✓ .XLS / .XLSX
- ✓ .PPT / .PPTX
- ✓ .CSV
- ✓ .PDF
- ✓ Photo Format (e.g., .JPEG, .PNG)
- ✓ Video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .AVI)

3.3.5 Work Package 5

Type of collected data

- Technical data
- Stakeholders data
- Other

Aim of data collected in WP5

WP5 – ‘Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation’ ensures wide visibility of the MARINEWIND project, implementing an effective communication and dissemination Plan and activities and paves the way for the exploitation of the project results. The main part of data collected in this WP is related to statistical data about the communication and dissemination activities. Statistical data about communication and dissemination activities will be generated by the main communication channels, i.e., website, social media accounts (see D5.1 Strategic Communication and Dissemination Plan). Other data collected will be personal data, i.e., subscribers to the project newsletter, list of participants to outreach events, and so on. The dataset with contact information from subscribers to the project mailing list/newsletter will include contact information such as name and email. The collected data is necessary for distributing the project updates. The dataset of stakeholders

registered to the support tool on the website may contain personal information, including name, short profile/short bio, affiliation, social media channels and email of the contact person.

Format of collected data

- ✓ DOC /.DOCX
- ✓ .XLS / .XLSX
- ✓ .PPT / .PPTX
- ✓ .CSV
- ✓ .PDF
- ✓ Photo Format (e.g., .JPEG, .PNG)
- ✓ Video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .AVI)

3.3.6 Work Package 6

Type of collected data

- Technical data
- Stakeholders data
- Other

Aim of this data

This WP aims at ensuring: i) effective consortium coordination and project management according to the description of action; including the relevant administrative and financial procedures, communication within the consortium and with EC as well project meetings organisation; ii) appropriate data management and personal data protection in line with EU rules. The data collected is related to financial aspects of the projects (i.e., costs declarations of the consortium partners) and the internal consortium meetings, and it comprises meeting minutes, presentations, and recordings. Additional data could be generated through internal survey to collect feedback regarding specific issues related to project management.

Format of collected data

- ✓ .DOC /.DOCX
- ✓ .XLS / .XLSX
- ✓ .PPT / .PPTX
- ✓ .CSV
- ✓ .PDF
- ✓ Photo Format (e.g., .JPEG, .PNG)
- ✓ Video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .AVI)

4 DATA STORAGE AND BACK-UP

MARINEWIND involves the collaboration between 7 beneficiaries and 2 associated partners, thus a

moderate amount of data will be generated in various activities. To manage such quantities of data, with the aim to follow the FAIR principles and to stimulate the collaboration among partners, a few data storage tools have been selected. The selection was made having in mind the purposes and the end-users of the data stored, divided in tools appropriate for internal use and daily project activities, and tools for guaranteeing the long-term storage of MARINEWIND data.

List of storage tools NOT appropriate for long-term storing of data generated by MARINEWIND project but used to carry out daily project activities:

- Microsoft SharePoint: is a file hosting service and synchronization service operated by Microsoft as part of its web version of Office. It is a private space, created for the project activities (as detailed in MARINEWIND D6.6 Project Management Plan, M2), used by all beneficiaries and associated partners to share working files and store temporary master copy of raw data that should be available for use by other beneficiaries or associated partners for data processing.
- Local drives, company cloud storage and external portable storage devices: these are storage facilities that do not fall under surveillance of this data management plan. These are very common and convenient for individual short-term storage of data.

List of storage tools appropriate for long-term storing of data and to guarantee the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of data generated by MARINEWIND:

- ZENODO: A MARINEWIND ZENODO community has been created. MARINEWIND datasets will be stored there. Data files are versioned. The uploaded data is archived as a Submission Information Package. Derivatives of data files are generated, but original content is never modified. All data files are stored in CERN Data Centres, primarily Geneva, with replicas in Budapest. Data files are kept in multiple replicas in a distributed file system, which is backed up to tape on a nightly basis. All data files are stored along with a MD5 checksum of the file content. Files are regularly checked against their checksums to assure that file content remains constant. Each beneficiary has the possibility to upload the data produced by their project activities in the community and a moderator will validate it. Each dataset will have a readme file.

Link: https://zenodo.org/communities/marinewind_project_repository/

5 DATA DOCUMENTATION

All data are documented to help interested users to clearly understand and reuse them. For this reason, descriptive and substantive (i.e., how the data should be read or interpreted) metadata will be elaborated and described in a readme.txt file complementing each dataset (see **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**).

Table 1 - Metadata included in the readme file of MARINEWIND data

Creator*	Main researchers involved in producing the data.
Title*	Name or title by which the dataset is known.
Contributor	Institution where the data was created or collected. A person or organization responsible for making contributions to the dataset.
Publisher	A holder of the data (including archives appropriate) or institution which submitted the work. Any others may be listed as contributors.
Publication year*	The year when the data was or will be made publicly available.
Date created*	Date the resource itself was put together; this could be a date range or a single date.
Description*	Concise description of the contents of the dataset. Describe the research objective, type of research, method of data collection and type of data.
Subject	Subject, keyword, or key phrase describing the resource.
Temporal coverage	Indicate the dates to which the data refer. Enter the year or beginning and ending dates.
Spatial coverage	Describe the geographic area to which the data refer (e.g., municipality, town/city, region, country). The geographic coordinates of the area may be included, if desired.
Identifier	ZENODO automatically assigns a DOI to a dataset once the entire deposit procedure has been completed. In some cases, a dataset may be known by one or more other (persistent) identifiers.
Language*	The primary language of the resource.
Link to publication	Include the web addresses or DOIs for any publication, important internal reports or other datasets that are related to your dataset.

File naming & Identifiers

In MARINEWIND project, an identifier is used as a reference number or name for a data object, to make it easily findable. The identifier is a key part of our documentation and metadata. **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.** shows the codes that can be used for making identifiers.

Table 2 - Examples of files identification

Description	Deliverables	Meetings	Conferences/Events
First Letters	MARINEWIND	MARINEWIND	MARINEWIND
Underscore	–	–	–
Next letters	Deliverable number (Dx.y) [x=WP number, y=deliverable number]	Type of document (i.e., Agenda, Minutes, Presentation). In case of presentations, mention WP number as well.	Event title
Underscore	–	–	–

Next letters	Short explanatory title for the document	Location and date of the meeting separated by underscore	Location and date of the meeting separated by underscore
Underscore		–	–
Next letters		Short name of organisation and initials of presenter	Short name of organisation and initials of presenter
Underscore		–	–
Last letters	"v" and number of revision of this specific report [v0.1=draft version, v1.0=final version]	"v" and number of revision of this specific report [v0.1=draft version, v1.0=final version]	"v" and number of revision of this specific report [v0.1=draft version, v1.0=final version]

6 DATA ACCESS

The main part of raw and processed data generated by the project will be accessible to all consortium partners. It will be stored in MARINEWIND SharePoint site. Only members of consortium, after validation from the group administrator (i.e., APRE), can access this space. The public data will be accessible by ZENODO.

The data containing personal data and the data gathered through questionnaires, interviews, focus groups, workshops and through other data gathering methods used during the project will be anonymised, and therefore the data cannot be traced back to the individual. Data will be stored only in anonymous forms so the identities of the participants will only be known by the research partners involved. The data will be used only within the project and will not be made accessible for any third party unless authorised by the individual informant via informed consent. Raw data like interview protocols and audio files will be shared within the consortium partners and with external open repositories only upon agreement of the participants (agreement via informed consent) and in anonymised form. The stored data will not contain the names or addresses of participants and will be edited for full anonymity before being processed (e.g., in project reports). In case of sharing the data in an open repository, the following formats would be shared: audio files, transcripts, aggregated files, interview guidelines. Finally, citizen science data reports based on interviews, focus group and other data gathering methods will be based on aggregated information and comprise anonymous quotations respectively.

Confidential data and data collected for internal purposes will be stored in the secure facilities of the organization responsible for collecting the data and will be retained for two years after the end of the project. If requested and agreed by the participants, data can be shared with other consortium members through the online repository.

In case of data that cannot be accessible to public, it will be stored in ZENODO (to preserve it) but only the metadata will be public (In CC 0).

Details concerning the ownership, transfer and dissemination of projects results are defined in section 8 of the MARINEWIND Consortium Agreement and shall be followed accordingly. The relevant rules of the Grant Agreement, in specific Article 13, Article 15, Article 16 and Annex 5, are also relevant and apply accordingly.

7 DATA SHARING AND REUSE

MARINEWIND beneficiaries and associated partners will be the main users of data produced in the project. In MARINEWIND, all data may be classified into open, sensitive, and closed. Access depends on the classification of the data.

- Open data must be acknowledged by citing the data set. Permission from the researcher is not required.
- Sensitive (or confidential/restricted data) may be made available by the researcher after any identifying information has been removed. Then, they can be used and cited. Permission from the researcher could be sought.
- Closed data are not available for sharing.

In any case, the main part of MARINEWIND data will have the CC-BY license.

Details concerning the ownership, transfer and dissemination of projects results are defined in section 8 of the MARINEWIND Consortium Agreement and shall be followed accordingly. The relevant rules of the Grant Agreement, in specific Article 13, Article 15, Article 16 and Annex 5, are also relevant and apply accordingly.

8 DATA PRESERVATION AND ARCHIVING

All relevant obtained data will be preserved and archived in ZENODO. All data and items on ZENODO will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.

9 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

There are no specific costs to make MARINEWIND datasets FAIR, since no specific paid software is used and there are no costs for using specific repositories.

10 PRIVACY OF PARTICIPANTS

Since MARINEWIND activities involve the processing of personal data, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (GDPR) and other relevant EU-level^[1] and relevant national legal acts shall be complied with and respected by the consortium as a whole, as well as by each project Beneficiary and Associated Partner which will deal with personal data processing in the context of project implementation. To confirm compliance with the applicable EU and national legislation, each MARINEWIND beneficiary and associated partner signed a '**Declaration on Horizon Europe Ethical Standards and Data protection**' (all signed declarations are presented in the MARINEWIND

deliverable **D6.4 - Ethical Issue Reports**).

According to Art. 4(1) of GDPR, **personal data** ‘means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person’. Examples of personal data protection typically cover: names and surname, home and email address, an identification card number, location data and IP address or a cookie ID. **Processing of personal data** is defined in Art. 4(2) of the Regulation and means ‘any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organization, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction’.

In its Art. 5, the GDPR provides for the **principles of personal data processing**, stating that personal data must be:

- ‘processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject (‘lawfulness, fairness and transparency’);
- collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes (...) (‘purpose limitation’);
- adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed (‘data minimization’);
- accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date; every reasonable step must be taken to ensure that personal data that are inaccurate, having regard to the purposes for which they are processed, are erased, or rectified without delay (‘accuracy’);
- kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed (...) (‘storage limitation’);
- processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorized or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction, or damage, using appropriate technical or organizational measures (‘integrity and confidentiality’).

^[1] Regulation (EC) N° 45/2001 of the European Parliament and the Council of 18 December 2000 in the protection of individuals regarding the processing of personal data by the Community institutions and bodies and on the free movement of such data, Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purpose of prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences, Directive 2000/31/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 8 June 2000 on certain legal aspects of information society services, in particular electronic commerce in the Internal Market, Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector.

^[2] According to Art. 4(7) GDPR, ‘controller’ means the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data; where the purposes and means of such processing are determined by Union or Member State law, the controller or the specific criteria for its nomination may be provided for by Union or Member State law.

To fulfil to the GDPR requirements, there is a set of indications that each MARINEWIND Beneficiary and Associated Partner dealing with data processing will respect during the project implementation:

1) Consent

The consent should be given by an individual (data subject) in a free, specific, informed, and unambiguous manner, by way of a request presented in clear and plain language. Moreover, the consent should be given by an affirmative act, such as checking a box online or signing a form.

2) Providing transparent information

Individuals must be clearly informed on who is processing their personal data as well as what data will be processed, why and how. In addition to the above information, individuals should be also informed about who will receive the data, how long the data will be stored, the individual’s data protection rights (i.e., right to access, correction, erasure, restriction, objection, portability, etc.), whether there is a statutory or contractual obligation to provide the data and how consent can be withdrawn.

3) Ensuring the right to access and right to data portability

Individuals must be ensured with the right to request access to their personal data, free of charge and in an accessible format. In addition, when the processing is based on consent or a contract, the individual can ask for their personal data to be returned or transmitted to another company (right to portability).

4) Ensuring the right to erasure (right to be forgotten)

An individual has the right to request the data controller to erase their personal data, such as when the data is no longer needed to fulfil the processing purpose. The data controller is not obliged to comply with such request if: the processing is necessary to respect one’s freedom of expression and information, they must keep the personal data to comply with a legal obligation; there are other reasons of public interest to keep the personal data, such as public health or scientific and historical research purposes; they need to keep the personal data to establish a legal claim.

5) Ensuring the right to correct and right to object

If an individual thinks that their personal data is incorrect, incomplete, or inaccurate, they have the right to have it rectified or completed without undue delay.

6) Obligation of data protection by design and by default

To minimise privacy risks and increase trust, a data controller must take all necessary steps (e.g.,

pseudonymisation) to implement the data protection principles and protect the rights of individuals (data protection by design). In accordance with the obligation of data protection by default, the entity processing personal data should ensure that the most privacy friendly setting is the default setting.

7) Obligation to provide proper notification in the case of a data breach

In case a data breach occurs, and the breach poses a risk to individual rights and freedoms, the entity processing personal data should notify the relevant Data Protection Authority within 72 hours after becoming aware of the breach. If the data breach poses a high risk to those affected, the entity may also be required to inform all individuals affected by the data breach.

Details on specific measures that will be taken by each MARINEWIND Beneficiary and Associated Partner to safeguard the rights and freedoms of MARINEWIND data subjects, and the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to their personal data are provided in MARINEWIND deliverable D6.4 - Ethical Issue Reports (in Appendix 1 in the '**Declaration on Horizon Europe Ethical Standards and Data protection**' of each Beneficiary and Associated Partner, in the part related to the privacy policy of the Beneficiary).